

A Theoretical Framework for Blockchain and Solidity in decentralized federated Learning

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Abstract— This paper proposes a theoretical approach that integrates blockchain technology and solidity based smart contracts to tackle the limitation of Federated learning. Federated learning is a privacy preserving movement for training the model without exposing the confidential raw data across decentralized data sources. However, the advantage seems promising, the major concern is still lack of trust between the participants and vulnerability to malicious updates. The proposed architecture has decentralized connection of model training and aggregation, prioritizing data privacy and providing traceability. This work aims on focusing on the design and feasibility analysis of combining the security advancement of blockchain and smart contract to federated learning for future implementation and simulation research studies in decentralized AI systems.

Keywords— Federated Learning, Blockchain, Solidity, Smart Contracts, Privacy, Incentives, AI Security

I. INTRODUCTION

In a dominating era of data-driven artificial intelligence, the security approach in every step is a must, especially in sensitive domains such as healthcare, finance, and smart devices. Considering these, Federated learning has raised as a promising approach that proposes decentralized training of machine learning models without sharing of raw and sensitive data. Instead, each branch or a participant trains the model locally with the secured data and returns only the updates, thus preventing the data (Abbas et al., 2024). However, the narrow side of federated learning is still problematic, introducing new challenges. Data are secured at a certain level but internally in the system, lack of trust between participants and potential for false update introduce a new serious challenge (Qammar et al., 2022).

In this scenario, use of blockchain technology aligns with all possible challenges and prevents it. Blockchain is known for its decentralized approach, immutability and transparency. Addition of solidity-based smart contract, can automate update verification, aggregation, and reward distribution to maintain honest connection within a federated learning environment (Ning et al., 2024). The whole concept revolves around tracking the loopholes of the federated system and designing conceptual ways and analyzing its feasibility of such system for solving with a blockchain approach methods.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Federated Learning

Federated learning (FL) is a decentralized approach under machine learning which allows multiple clients—such as institution, hospital to train model locally without leakage of the raw sensitive data. The initial model is distributed to the clients and each respective performs model training in the local data and only gives back the model updates to the main point. This workflow preserves data privacy and increases trust in the system (Narmadha & Varalakshmi, 2022). In sensitive domains like healthcare, finance where visitor data cannot be centralized or shared, Federated learning is very useful. However, the security concern still remains in question on a certain level. FL in some system rises question on lack of trust among the participants itself and it has risk of getting false or malicious update which can hinder the overall approach objective (Saha et al., 2024).

Fig 1: Overview of Federated Learning Process

B. Blockchain in Federated Learning

Blockchain, a decentralized technology that maintains transparency across the system so that nothing goes unnoticed. It makes sure that no changes occur without a proper source (Senarathna, 2025). In the context of Federated learning (FL), Blockchain covers various loopholes providing solution to the limitation of FL.

In this concept, the model updates can be recorded in the chain, blockchain creates a record of contribution, reduces the risk of unwanted manipulation and unauthorized access (Yin et al., 2024). This makes the overall system more robust and improves security and fairness. The sole purpose of use of blockchain technology in FL is for enhancing trustworthiness and accountability of FL system.

C. Solidity and Smart Contracts

Solidity is a programming language that is oriented around contracts. It is actually used to write smart contracts on Ethereum and also other blockchain platform. Inside federated learning, smart contracts can auto make various important processes—such as verifying model updates, aggregating contributions securely, and distributing rewards (Wang et al., 2024). Use of smart contracts reduces dependency on central authority with enhancing fairness and transparency. These contracts work on tamper-proof environment, when the logic and mechanism once written cannot be altered again. Use of smart contract adds on a reliable layer for contribution tracking, monitoring, and reward distribution without central dependency (Wang et al., 2022).

D. Recent Trends

The recent trends in federated learning revolves around decentralized and security. Traditional implementation was dependent on a central authority that used to distribute the workflow. In recent times, blockchain has been introduced as a coordination layer. Moreover, incentive mechanism is involved for honest participation through reputation-based systems (Ngoupayou Limbepe et al., 2025). Many studies have mentioned the benefits of using smart contracts to automate tasks. These trends show a growing overlapping interest of federated learning, blockchain, and cryptographic techniques aimed at building distributed AI systems that is aware of data privacy. Every solution purposed are related to security and trustworthy concerns (Moudoud & Cherkaoui, 2023).

III. PROPOSED THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual architecture is discussed in this section for implementing blockchain and solidity into federated learning system. The proposed framework is targeted to provide a solution for the issues in traditional FL systems. The aim is to provide an approach for solving crucial issues like lack of trust, and verifiability.

A. System Architecture

The overview of the system is built in three main blocks: Federated learning (FL) Nodes, a blockchain layer, and a smart contract Layer. As shown in the figure, the FL notes refers to—research institutes, hospitals, or any edge devices.

So, looking at the figure, FL nodes locally train Machine learning models on the private data and generate the encrypted model updates. But, these updates are not directly shared with any central authority. But instead, they are submitted to a decentralized environment for verification and coordination.

That is where the block of blockchain and Smart contract comes in. The blockchain acts as a transparent, tamper—resistance medium that maintains the data related with submitted model updates. It makes sure that no central authorization is needed to maintain integrity and trust.

Just above this, lies a smart contract layer—which is implemented in Solidity. That is present for the automation of the key operations like update submission, verification, global model coordination and incentive distribution. The smart contract layer validates every moral contribution and updates based on the predefined criteria. Then, It will be easier for the aggregation process. Where the objects are eligible to be included in the global model. This way by. The influence of every layer such as blockchain layer and smart contract layer, there would be no question left for the lack of trust among the participants in the Federated learning environment.

Fig 2: System Architecture

B. Smart Contract Functions

The smart contract layer is present as an automatic logic of decentralized federated learning (FL) Framework. It handles all the key operations like update submission, verification, aggregation coordination and also reward distribution. This use of smart contracts removes the need for centralized control and will establish trust among participants. By implementing and executing logic on chain the smart contract makes sure that all contributions and updates are transparent and verified securely (Ramanan & Nakayama, 2020).

The framework defines a series of smart contract functions, which includes **submitUpdate**, this allows every FL node to submit its contribution in model in a form of hashed reference. This step makes sure that the sensitive data and model remains confidential while still being submitted.

In the other hand. The function **verifyUpdate**, it does regular check to access the validity of each contribution., this may involve threshold checks on metadata like accuracy proof of training, timestamps. Furthermore, the function **distributeRewards** calculates and. provides the rewards based on the matrices, such as performance improvement or computational effort.

These core function of smart contracts are complemented by event functions to provide traceability of interactions. Overall, use of smart contract layer provides a secure flow under federated learning lifecycle in a decentralized manner.

C. Workflow of the system

Fig 3: WorkFlow Diagram

The workflow of the overall system iterates across training rounds under sequence of interactions among FL nodes, the blockchain and the smart contract layer. The flow begins with individual FL nodes—such as institution or edge devices, performing model training in private data at local level. There is no exchange of raw data; instead the updates of model are generated and those are the once that are shared in a form of hashed or encrypted parameters.

After local model training all the updates are submitted by the nodes to the blockchain through smart contract interface, using function—such as **submitUpdate** and **verifyUpdate**. These smart contract function do the respective purposed task of recording metadata associated with each submission, ensuring update is linked to the submitted node and is permanently auditable and submitted updates are evaluated based upon benchmarks and contribution uniqueness. And, Then the updates are legit assets for global model. Once the verification stage is cleared, the selected updates are aggregated using method like federated Averaging or more advance approaches. And, for encouraging participation and honest behaviors the **distributeRewards** function it executed, that distributes and allocates token-based rewards to contributors.

This particular workflow loop continues for multiple rounds until the model performance keeps improving while maintaining transparency, privacy and trust through blockchain and smart contract.

IV. FRAMEWORK CONSIDERATIONS AND APPLICABILITY

After theoretical potential this section of the report presents practical way for implementing the proposed blockchain enabled FL system. It highlights potential use case. This section helps to understand the relevance of the theoretical aspect in real life. And its limitations.

A. Use case Scenario

One of the most convincing use of this framework can be seen in the healthcare domain, where the privacy and data security is very important. In this particular situation, healthcare institution cannot share the patient data due to legal and ethical concerns (Moulahi et al., 2023). Nevertheless, there is always an upper hand on implementing several disease early predictions for patient own safety and precaution steps.

By implementing federated learning with enhanced security with smart contract, each hospital will train a model locally on its private data of patients. Then, the updates of the model are submitted blockchain through smart contract layer. Through smart contract layer the updates are verified, aggregated, and also rewarded in a secure transparent manner. This allows for a smooth way to create highly accurate model for health research and diagnosis purpose without exposing the sensitive patient data. Furthermore, the encourage mechanism will increase participation by rewarding institution based on their contribution.

B. Assumptions

For a precise redemption of the theoretical implementation, participating FL nodes like a health institute are assumed to follow the protocol and may attempt to maximize the rewards. Smart contract is placed for a intensive verification and to have a traceable submission for eliminating malicious behavior. At the final step, the aggregation of final model is done off-chain which means it is assumed that secure and trusted mechanisms are used for that specific purpose. The data stored on-chain would be only metadata and reference to the model updates not the entire model keeping cost efficiency in mind. And lastly, the framework assumes that there is stable internet connection and blockchain availability to avoid time match fluctuation for events like verification and secure model updates.

C. Design Constraints

In federated learning, many nodes frequently submit the updates and have them verified and receive or update global model but in blockchain , specially the public ones like Ethereum or blockchain can only process a limited number of transaction per second and take several seconds to be confirmed (Khan et al., 2021). This may slowdown the FL rounds. Execution of smart contracts has gas fees and frequent interactions and transaction could be costly.

As the aggregation of the updates must occur off-chain due to consideration of computational and cost efficiency, this makes a dependency on external component so those must be secure and trusted. On an overlook of the system flow of the FL system, they may be complex and limited storage and processing capacity can always be a problem.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a framework highlighting the problem in FL systems and discussing how can implementation of blockchain concept can help regarding that by addressing key challenges—such as trust and data privacy. By implementing the immutability and transparent feature of blockchain and automation through smart contract, the proposed framework promotes a decentralized alternative to traditional FL system. The integrated system makes sure that the model updates can securely be submitted, verified and rewarded, reducing the need for central control.

The framework approach highlights a design consisting of FL nodes, a blockchain layer, and a smart contract layer, with an iterative workflow that prioritizes privacy preserving model training. A use case is demonstrated for its guidance on practical implementation. The assumptions and design obstacle are present showcasing the problem to be solved as future refinement. Overall, this work contributes for building decentralized, collaborative work environment and AI ecosystem for sensitive data environment.

VI. REFERENCE

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